

Interaction of Tetrachlorides of Silicon, Titanium, Zirconium, Tin, and Thorium with Phenylacetic Acid

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Reactions of tetrachlorides of silicon, titanium, zirconium, tin, and thorium with phenylacetic acid have been studied. Silicon tetrachloride yields a *tetra* substitute, titanium tetrachloride forms all the four, *i.e.*, mono, di, tri, and tetra, whereas zirconium and thorium produce di, tri, and tetra and mono, di, and tri substitutes respectively. Stannic tetrachloride does not form any substitution product.

Action of acetic acid on silicon tetrachloride has been reported by Taurke¹, Montonna², and Kapoor *et al.*³ and interactions of silicon, titanium, zirconium, tin, and thorium tetrachlorides and organic acids, *e.g.*, propionic, salicylic, and formic, have already been studied in this laboratory⁴. In the present communication actions of phenylacetic acid with silicon, titanium, zirconium, tin, and thorium tetrachlorides have been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Phenylacetic acid was purified by repeated crystallisations from hot water, dried in an air oven at 60° for over an hour, and then cooled in a vacuum desiccator⁵.

Titanium tetrachloride was purified by keeping over copper turnings for about 12 hours and then distilling over a fractionating column. The distillate at 136.4° was collected for use. Zirconium tetrachloride used was of B. D. H. extra pure quality whereas the rest of the chemicals were purified by the usual methods⁴.

Silicon tetrachloride was allowed to react with a large excess of phenylacetic acid, dissolved in minimum quantity of pure dry ether, in a r.b. flask fitted with a water condenser and a guard tube. The temperature was slowly raised to and maintained at 60° for several hours till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas had ceased, but no solid separated. The reaction mixture, which solidified on cooling, was purified by repeated washings and then recrystallisations from dry ether, and dried in vacuum. Analysis corresponded to the composition $\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{COO})_4$. All attempts to prepare other substitutes proved futile.

*Same as Kundan Lal.

1. *Ber.*, 1905, **38**, 1668.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 2114.

3. *This Journal*, 1958, **35**, 157.

4. Jaura and Bajwa, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, **20B**, 301.

5. Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, Green & Co., New York, 1956, 3rd ed., p. 781.

Phenylacetic acid, dissolved in ether, was added in convenient instalments to titanium tetrachloride at 0°. The reaction being exothermic with a brisk evolution of hydrogen chloride gas, the reaction mixture was cooled to 0° before each addition of the acid. Finally the temperature was slowly raised to and maintained at 60° for several hours, resulting in the formation of a yellow crystalline solid, $Ti(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_4$. Similarly with calculated quantities of the reactants mono, di and, tri substitutes were prepared.

Both zirconium tetrachloride and phenylacetic acid (in excess) were heated on a water bath at 80°. The reaction started with the evolution HCl gas and after about 3 hours it yielded a yellow paste. The temperature was slowly raised to and maintained at 110° for about 5 hours in an oil bath when the reaction stopped and a yellow solid, $ZrCl_2(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_2$, separated, but on keeping the reaction mixture at 135° similarly for about 15 hours, the end product was $Zr(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_4$. On heating the reactants in calculated quantities at 120° for several hours in a similar way, $ZrCl(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_3$ was obtained and all attempts for mono substitute failed.

Stannic tetrachloride did not yield any product with phenylacetic acid.

Thorium tetrachloride, when heated to 65° for 6 to 7 hours with a large excess of phenylacetic acid, gave $ThCl_2(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_2$. Similarly tri substitute (at 100° for 4 hours) and mono substitute (at 30° for 3 hours) were obtained. Tetra substitute could not be prepared at all and the end product was always the tri substitute.

TABLE I

Substitution products of silicon, titanium, zirconium, tin, and thorium tetrachlorides with phenylacetic acid.

Tetrachloride.	Formula.	Obs.	Calc.	Physical state.
$SiCl_4$	$Si(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_4$	Si : 4.90%	4.94%	White crystalline solid decomposing above 320° without melting.
$TiCl_4$	$TiCl_3(C_6H_5CH_2COO)$	Ti : 16.43 Cl : 36.88	16.50 36.80	Yellowish brown sticky hygroscopic mass.
	$TiCl_2(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_2$	Ti : 11.90 Cl : 16.90	12.23 16.00	Reddish viscous mass.
	$TiCl(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_3$	Ti : 10.40 Cl : 8.20	9.80 7.26	Reddish brown sticky mass.
	$Ti(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_4$	Ti : 7.85	8.14	Yellowish crystalline compound melting at 70-72°.
$ZrCl_4$	$ZrCl_2(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_2$	Zr : 20.70 Cl : 15.08	21.12 16.40	Yellow powder decomposing at 170° without melting.
	$ZrCl(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_3$	Zr : 18.05 Cl : 7.43	17.20 6.67	Yellowish amorphous powder melting at 133-35°.
	$Zr(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_4$	Zr : 13.92	14.40	Brownish solid melting at 123°.
$SnCl_4$	..	..	..	..
$ThCl_4$	$ThCl_3(C_6H_5CH_2COO)$	Th : 43.20 Cl : 21.75	49.00 22.60	White powder decomposing above 300° without melting.
	$ThCl_2(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_2$	Th : 39.70 Cl : 11.80	40.50 12.21	White powder decomposing above 300° without melting.
	$ThCl(C_6H_5CH_2COO)_3$	Th : 33.90 Cl : 4.95	34.50 5.28	White light solid decomposing above 300° without melting.

DISCUSSION

Apart from the nature of the tetrachlorides, the reacting substances also contribute significantly in such reactions. For example, acetic acid and benzoic acid do not yield higher substitutes with titanium tetrachloride⁶, nor does benzoic acid with ethyl and isopropyl titanates⁶. But phenylacetic acid behaves in a different way and produces all the possible substitutes with titanium tetrachloride, di, tri, and tetra with zirconium tetrachloride, and mono, di, and tri with thorium tetrachloride. Zirconium tetrachloride shows a greater tendency to form higher substitutes and its mono substitute is therefore not detected at all. Tetra substitute of thorium, due to a very heavy molecule, perhaps develops an unstable character and therefore is either not formed at all or decomposes immediately to a lower substitute. The reaction does not, however, proceed beyond the formation of a tri substitute. Formation of higher substitutes with phenylacetic acid in the present investigation, as compared with those formed with acetic acid⁶ and benzoic acid, reported earlier, suggests that the replacement of one hydrogen atom by a phenyl group in acetic acid causes an overall increase in the stability of these substitution products.

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